

The "On the Divine Names" of Pseudo Denys the Areopagite

By Lampros Alexopoulos, University of Thessaloniki

Entry tags: Neoplatonism, Early Christianity, Religious Group, Greek Philosophical Traditions, Text, Christian Traditions, Ancient Greek text, Christian Mysticism, Greek Religions, Mysticism, Christian Theology

The treatise "On the Divine Names" is written by Pseudo Denys (Dionysius) the Areopagite. The treatise extends to thirteen chapters which, when completed, leaves the reader intrigued and fascinated from the beautiful "spectacles" it contains: the infinite manifestation of God's providence; the silent reconciling effect of divine peace; the connecting power of divine eros; the undisputed dominance of the good that pervades everything; the unity of everything in the absolute one, God. Its author presents himself as Dionysius the Areopagite, originally a member of the Athenian judicial council (known as 'the Areopagus') in the 1st century C.E. who was converted by Paul and became his disciple (mentioned in "Acts" 17:34). For this reason, Dionysius's writings retained the status of apostolic authority until the 19th century, when studies proved that the author was deeply influenced by the Athenian Neoplatonic school of Proclus. Hence, the treatise was written in the time of Proclus (ca. 500, since Proclus died in 485 CE and since Severus of Antioch explicitly cites Dionysius's writings between the years 518-528) by one of his pupils, perhaps of Syrian origin, who knew enough of Platonism and the Christian tradition. The treatise is Dionysius's longest work. It consists of thirteen chapters and deals with affirmative theology, namely, the names attributed to God in the Scripture. It furthermore explores the limits and the capacities of human language, also involving negative theology. Dionysius deals particularly with the distinction into the multiple attributes of the godhead as a whole. Although the names applied to the godhead refer to it as a unity, each name however is different and it therefore differentiates the godhead. Dionysius's use of the prefix "over-" indicates the self-multiplication of the godhead, while the use of the prefix "pre-" indicates that God has the attributes of creatures in such a way that he transcends both creature and attribute. The so-called "Corpus Areopagiticum" became extremely popular in the Latin West when the Byzantine emperor Michael II the Stammerer (770-829) sent a copy as a gift to king Louis the Pious in 827. The first translation, made in 838 by the abbot Hilduin of the monastery of Saint Denys near Paris, was so incomprehensible that Charles II the Bald asked John Scottus Eriugena to make a new translation, completed in 862 and revised in 875. The influence of Dionysius in Eriugena's thought is profound. Dionysius's writings also had a profound effect in the Franciscan tradition, especially in Robert Grosseteste and Bonaventure. Dionysius's ideas pervade not only the Italian and English Renaissance, but also the German mystical writers (Mystique rhénane; Rheinländische Mystik), such as Meister Eckhart, Jean Tauler, John van Ruysbroeck, Jean Charlier de Gerson, not to mention Nicholas of Cusa and the Spanish mystics, such as St. John of the Cross.

Date Range: 485 CE - 528 CE

Region: Syria.

Region tags: Middle East, Syria

Syria, probably the country of origin of the author of the "On the Divine Names".

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Beate Regina Suchla. *Corpus Dionysiacum I*. Berlin: de Gruyter, 1990.
- Source 2: Günter Heil and Adolf Martin Ritter. *Corpus Dionysiacum II*. Berlin: de Gruyter, 1991.
- Source 3: Colm Luibheid and Paul Rorem, trans. *Pseudo-Dionysius: The Complete Works*. New York: Paulist Press, 1987.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/pseudo-dionysius-areopagite/#AftSigInf>
- Source 1 Description: Pseudo-Dionysius the Areopagite-Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Pseudo-Dionysius-the-Areopagite>
- Source 2 Description: Pseudo-Dionysius the Areopagite-Britannica
- Source 3 URL: http://dysinger.stjohnsem.edu/@texts/0500_dion_aer/00a_start.htm
- Source 3 Description: DIONYSIUS THE AREOPAGITE

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://archive.org/details/worksofdionysius00pseu/page/n9/mode/2up>
- Source 1 Description: The works of Dionysius the Areopagite
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.ccel.org/ccel/rolt/dionysius.html>
- Source 2 Description: Dionysius the Areopagite: On the Divine Names and the Mystical Theology

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Methods of Composition

– Written

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Inked

–with Ink

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Papyrus

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Inked

– with Ink

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Papyrus

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text
This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is there material significance to the text?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Supernatural beings care about other

–Specify: No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Vocabulary

Notes: The text bears the stamp of later Neoplatonism, especially in its linguistic expression. The author uses a very original and very refined theological terminology. This terminology very close to that of the Greek mysteries. Such a language, however, was freely and consciously subjugated and transformed within the Christian Church already from the Alexandrians of the second century, as well as the theologians of the fourth century.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Calligraphy?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Illustrations?

— Yes

Notes: Although Ps. Dionysius is not a real person but its author pseudonymously presents himself as Dionysius the Areopagite, several Western medieval manuscripts contain illustrations depicting him. The actual Denys the Areopagite, a member of the Athenian judicial council who lived in the 1st century C.E. and converted by Paul and became his disciple, is revered as a saint by the Orthodox Church. Therefore, there are pictures, miniatures in manuscripts and church murals that depict the real Denys the Areopagite.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Illuminations?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The text consists a part of the Areopagetic Corpus. The Corpus contains the following works: 1. On

the Divine Names 2. Celestial Hierarchy 3. Ecclesiastical Hierarchy 4. Mystical Theology 5. Ten epistles
Moreover, the Corpus contains references to a series of other works written by the same author. This however is most probably a mere literary myth. Letters, which bear the signature of Ps. Denys and were preserved only in Latin translation and letters discovered in Syrian and Armenian translations, belong to other authors.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is there a sense of canonization?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is the text part of a series of volumes?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require fasting?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Mystical theology

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: In his supreme existence, through his own principle, God is unknown and impossible to be explored. He is beyond all definitions, beyond the mind, the essence and the knowledge. It is impossible to feel, to imagine, to understand or to name God. He is completely hidden from the perceptive abilities of his creatures and goes beyond any measure that is accessible to our finite logic.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

— Yes

Notes: The first of the divine names that the author of the text attributes to God is "the good". Because of his goodness, God creates, gives life, and perfects everything. Just as the life-giving rays of the sun extend from its source in all directions, so the Supreme Good illuminates everything that exists with its unchanging radiance, and sends its sublime and life-giving rays - the rays of perfect goodness - in all directions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

—Specify: God is the perfect Beauty,

Notes: God is the perfect Beauty, the Super-beauty, the All-beauty, without beginning and end, without any defect or flaw — the source and model of all beauty. God is the beginning of everything and the end of all, because everything exists for him and they take their beauty from him.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Can reward

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Can punish

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: God has the attributes of creatures in such a way that he transcends both creature and attribute.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Notes: Albeit impossible to feel, imagine, understand or to name God, it does not mean that he is far from the world or that he hides himself from human beings. God is revealed and acts and is present in the creation, since this latter exists and remains and lives by this omnipresent presence of God. God is present in the world through and with his "works" and his goodness, which brings him into communion with all that exists.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ In dreams

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ In trance possession

– Yes

Notes: A certain level of knowledge can be acquired through an incomprehensible union with God. This is possible only with ecstasy, with overcoming all limits, with a kind of mental frenzy. This means entering into a sacred darkness, the "darkness of ignorance", the "darkness of silence". This "leap" is true knowledge, but it is knowledge without words and ideas and therefore non-transmissible knowledge, and in fact not even fully accessible to the person that has achieved it, because no one can even describe it to himself.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Through divination practices

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: Through prayer.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Yes

Notes: A certain level of knowledge can be acquired through an incomprehensible union with God. This is possible only with ecstasy, with overcoming all limits, with a kind of mental frenzy. This means entering into a sacred darkness, the "darkness of ignorance", the "darkness of silence". This "leap" is true knowledge, but it is knowledge without words and ideas and therefore non-transmissible knowledge, and in fact not even fully accessible to the person that has achieved it, because no one can even describe it to himself

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?

– No

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?

– No

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?

– I don't know

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?

– No

↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: Extensive and detailed descriptions of the celestial hierarchy of conceivable beings exist in other works of the Areopagetic Corpus.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: There is no reference to a specific category of beings in the text.

Notes: On the contrary, the only category of beings mentioned is the beings with a different essence from that of God, that is, the beings created by God. These latter fall into the category of "created beings" and are referred to as such throughout the text. Extensive references to the hierarchy and the kind of beings that make up the Areopagetic universe is made in other texts of the Areopagetic Corpus.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Calligraphy?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Illustrations?

– Yes

Notes: Although Ps. Dionysius is not a real person but its author pseudonymously presents himself as Dionysius the Areopagite, several Western medieval manuscripts contain illustrations depicting him. The actual Denys the Areopagite, a member of the Athenian judicial council who lived in the 1st century C.E. and converted by Paul and became his disciple, is revered as a saint by the Orthodox Church. Therefore, Therefore, there are pictures, miniatures in manuscripts and church murals that depict the real Denys the Areopagite.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Illuminations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The text consists a part of the Areopagetic Corpus. The Corpus contains the following works: 1. On the Divine Names 2. Celestial Hierarchy 3. Ecclesiastical Hierarchy 4. Mystical Theology 5. Ten epistles Moreover, the Corpus contains references to a series of other works written by the same author. This however is most probably a mere literary myth. Letters, which bear the signature of Ps. Denys and were preserved only in Latin translation and letters discovered in Syrian and Armenian translations, belong to other authors.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Cultural with religious implications?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Behavioral literature?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Other

– Other [specify]: Mystical theology

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Vocabulary

Notes: The text bears the stamp of later Neoplatonism, especially in its linguistic expression. The author uses a very original and very refined theological terminology. This terminology very close to that of the Greek mysteries. Such a language, however, was freely and consciously subjugated and transformed within the Christian Church already from the Alexandrians of the second century, as well as the theologians of the fourth century.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: In his supreme existence, through his own principle, God is unknown and impossible to be explored. He is beyond all definitions, beyond the mind, the essence and the knowledge. It is impossible to feel, to imagine, to understand or to name God. He is completely hidden from the perceptive abilities of his creatures and goes beyond any measure that is accessible to our finite logic.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

Notes: The first of the divine names that the author of the text attributes to God is "the good". Because of his goodness, God creates, gives life, and perfects everything. Just as the life-giving rays of the sun extend from its source in all directions, so the Supreme Good illuminates everything that exists with its unchanging radiance, and sends its sublime and life-giving rays - the rays of perfect goodness - in all directions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: God is the perfect Beauty,

Notes: God is the perfect Beauty, the Super-beauty, the All-beauty, without beginning and end, without any defect or flaw – the source and model of all beauty. God is the beginning of everything and the end of all, because everything exists for him and they take their beauty from him.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Can reward

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Can punish

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: God has the attributes of creatures in such a way that he transcends both creature and attribute.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Notes: Albeit impossible to feel, imagine, understand or to name God, it does not mean that he is far from the world or that he hides himself from human beings. God is revealed and acts and is present in the creation, since this latter exists and remains and lives by this omnipresent presence of God. God is present in the world through and with his "works" and his goodness, which brings him into communion with all that exists.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

In dreams

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

In trance possession

– Yes

Notes: A certain level of knowledge can be acquired through an incomprehensible union with God. This is possible only with ecstasy, with overcoming all limits, with a kind of mental frenzy. This means entering into a sacred darkness, the "darkness of ignorance", the "darkness of silence". This "leap" is true knowledge, but it is knowledge without words and ideas and therefore non-transmissible knowledge, and in fact not even fully accessible to the person that has achieved it, because no one can even describe it to himself.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Through divination practices

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Only through religious specialists

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: Through prayer.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Yes

Notes: A certain level of knowledge can be acquired through an incomprehensible union with God. This is possible only with ecstasy, with overcoming all limits, with a kind of mental frenzy. This means entering into a sacred darkness, the "darkness of ignorance", the "darkness of silence". This "leap" is true knowledge, but it is knowledge without words and ideas and therefore non-transmissible knowledge, and in fact not even fully accessible to the person that has achieved it, because no one can even describe it to himself

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?

– No

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?

– No

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?

– I don't know

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?

– No

↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: Extensive and detailed descriptions of the celestial hierarchy of conceivable beings exist in other works of the Areopagetic Corpus.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: There is no reference to a specific category of beings in the text.

Notes: On the contrary, the only category of beings mentioned is the beings with a different essence from that of God, that is, the beings created by God. These latter fall into the category of "created beings" and are referred to as such throughout the text. Extensive references to the hierarchy and the kind of beings that make up the Areopagetic universe is made in other texts of the Areopagetic Corpus.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The text was reproduced in both East and West by both state officials and religious groups, such as Monastic orders.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The text was reproduced in both East and West by both state officials and religious groups, such as Monastic orders.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

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Specific to this answer:

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Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

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